

"Climate & Water" — interactive web platform for accessing climate data

Thank you for your interest in this study!

We advise that you use a desktop, laptop or tablet to best view the images and questions.

The survey forms part of a research collaboration between the **Environmental Protection Agency** and the **Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Institute of the SES of Ukraine and NAS of Ukraine**. Our study aims to improve understanding of how different visualisations of climate model data, particularly spatial data, are interpreted by people across regions, societal sectors and disciplines. More details on the research, including contact details, are provided at the end of the survey.

This form **does not collect personal data**. You can leave information about yourself only if you wish in the field at the end of the survey. Contact me if you have any additional questions natalia.nikitenko@uhmi.org.ua

The survey should take approximately **20 minutes** to complete.

Зірочка (*) указує, що запитання обов'язкове

2. Загальні питання

1. Please write the type of institution you work for and your position in it.

2. 2. What information about changes in water resources under future climate scenarios would be most useful for your operational and planning activities? *(Multiple answers possible)* *

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Annual changes in runoff and river discharge.
- Frequency of extreme events (e.g., droughts, floods).
- Groundwater availability and groundwater recharge rates.
- Changes in evaporation (evapotranspiration)
- Seasonal variations, including periods of low water levels throughout the year.
- Comparative analysis with historical data.
- Інше: _____

3. 3. In your opinion, please list 1-2 of the most devastating impacts of climate change on water resources. *(Multiple answers are possible)*

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Changes in water flow regime
- Increased frequency of extreme events (droughts/rainfalls/floods)
- Decrease in precipitation
- Increasing temperatures
- Deterioration of water quality (increased amount of pollutants, deterioration of oxygen regime, increased content of organic and biogenic substances, etc.)
- Impact on reservoirs and hydroelectric power plants
- Інше: _____

4. 4. What are the main challenges you face in managing your region's river basin in the face of climate change? *(Multiple answers possible)* *

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Absence/lack of data on the impact of climate change on water resources.
- Difficulties in responding to extreme weather events (e.g. floods, droughts).
- Problems with the management of transboundary rivers.
- Інше: _____

5. 5. Do you have enough information to plan and implement effective mitigation measures in your region's river basin? *

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- Yes, we have all the necessary information to plan and implement effective mitigation measures.
- Partially, but the information is not detailed enough for accurate planning.
- No, there is a significant lack of information, which makes it difficult to plan effective measures.
- Not sure because we haven't fully evaluated the available information.

6. 6. What is your primary source of information for long-term water resource allocation planning?

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- Charts or maps as well as underlying datasets generated on your own
- Charts or maps generated on your own based on provided datasets
- All kind of information (charts, map, tables) provided to you from external sources.
- A combination of your calculations (visualizations) and materials from external sources.
- Інше: _____

7. 7. Do you regularly use information from the sites **climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu**, **atlas.climate.copernicus.eu** in your work or indicate other platforms (websites) you regularly use data from.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu
- atlas.climate.copernicus.eu
- Інше: _____

3. Data visualization. Annual changes in river discharge.

8. **1. This chart shows historical and expected changes in annual river discharge at the outlet.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region?

Source: 10.1016/j.envc.2024.100899

Fig. 1. Historical and bias-corrected projected time series of the two Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs). The solid line represents the multi-model median, and the shaded area represents the corresponding bias-corrected simulation from 5 GCMs for river runoff. The trend rate at a 95 % confidence level is represented in bold and italic characters.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

9. **2. This chart shows historical and expected changes in annual runoff.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region?

Source: Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas

Fig. 2. Relative change in average annual water runoff relative to 1991-2020 under a high greenhouse gas emissions scenario (RCP8.5) for the EURO-CORDEX-11 ensemble of climate models.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

10. **3. This chart shows expected changes in annual river runoff.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region?

Source: 10.1016/j.envc.2024.100899

Fig. 3. Annual river runoff (a-b) percent change simulated by five GCMs under the SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 for the period of near future and far future compared to the historical period (1985 – 2014)

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

11. **4. This chart shows expected changes in annual river discharge at the outlet.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region?

Source: 10.1016/j.ejrh.2020.100761

Fig. 4. Projected changes in mean annual river discharge simulated by the WaterGAP2 model for eight river basins for two future periods under RCP2.6 and RCP 8.5. Upper box lines indicate 75th percentile, lower – 25th percentile and the middle lines present median; vertical lines show minimal and maximal values.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

4. Data visualization. Spatial changes in annual discharge (or water runoff) across the basin.

12. **1. This map shows the expected changes in annual discharge for the river network.**

Do you think this figure format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.2166/wcc.2021.034

Fig. 5. Change in mean annual flow (ΔQ , %) with standard deviation (SD, %) of the regional climate models (RCMs) ensemble under RCP8.5 for 2021-2050 and 2071-2100 over 1991-2020.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.

- 📖 The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- 😞 The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- 🚫 The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- 📝 It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- 🛠️ This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Ише: _____

13. **2. This map shows the expected changes in annual water runoff across the basin.**

Do you think this map format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.1002/hyp.7753

Fig. 6. Difference maps for the simulated mean water runoff between the climate scenario period 2051–2060 and the reference period 1961–1990 (a), and the standard deviations (b)

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

14. **3. This map shows the expected changes in annual water runoff across the basin.**

Do you think this map format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas

Fig. 7. Relative change in average annual runoff in the period 2021-2040 relative to 1991-2020 for the high greenhouse gas emissions scenario RCP8.5 according to the EURO-CORDEX ensemble of climate models.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

5. Data visualization. Intra-annual changes in discharge or runoff of a river basin

15. **4. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in runoff within the river basin.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas

Fig. 8. Relative change in runoff in the period 2021-2040 relative to 1991-2020 under the high greenhouse gas emissions scenario (RCP8.5) for the EURO-CORDEX-11 ensemble of climate models.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

16. **5. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in river discharge at the outlet.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.1016/j.ejrh.2020.100761

Fig. 9. Projected changes in the long-term mean monthly river discharge for two future periods under RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5. Colored ranges show how model spread and solid lines show multi model mean.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

17. **6. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in river discharge at the outlet.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Fig. 10. Long-term mean monthly developments of discharge [m³/s] according to the historical GCM-RCM-driven simulations (ensemble mean, 1971–2000) and the GCM-RCM-driven simulations (ensemble mean) under RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 for the near future (2031–2060) and the far future (2071–2100) for the Upper Danube at gauge Achleiten, the Middle Danube at gauge Iron Gate and the Lower Danube at gauge Ceatal Izmail.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

18. **7. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in river discharge at the outlet.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108378

Fig. 11. Seasonal percent changes in projected future (a) streamflow over the short-, medium-, and long-term periods under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios relative to the historical reference.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

19. **8. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in runoff across the basin.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.1016/j.ecohyd.2021.11.004

Fig. 12. Monthly results for precipitation and hydrological variables presented in units of mm/month.

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

20. **9. This graph shows the expected intra-annual changes in runoff across the basin.** *

Do you think this graph format would be appropriate for your needs if similar information were provided for the river basin in your region? *In your opinion:*

Source: 10.1016/j.ecohyd.2021.11.004

Fig. 13. Difference (in percent) in monthly median results for water flow presented in percentage change for mid-century and end-century scenarios relative to historical period

Виберіть лише один варіант.

- The graph contains all the information you need to make informed decisions.
- The necessary information is present, but additional calculations or analysis are required for effective use.
- The necessary information is partially present, but key details are missing.
- The necessary information is completely missing from the chart.
- It is not known how to interpret the data for practical recommendations or actions.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Інше: _____

6. Your experience using web resources for professional activities.

21. 1. In your experience, what challenges have you encountered when using studies or reports that provide information about future climate change for water resources management? *(Multiple answers possible)* *

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Difficulties in interpreting general climate change estimates into specific local changes.
- Difficulty understanding research assumptions and limitations.
- Lack of updates or ongoing support in research to reflect new data or trends.
- Limited access to comprehensive, detailed, or relevant research for your specific region or needs.
- Contradictions in results or conclusions between different studies, which complicates the decision-making process.
- Insufficient detail on how climate change impacts translate into practical water management issues.
- Difficulties in integrating scientific reports with the formulation of policies or exploitation strategies.
- Інше: _____

22. 2. What general difficulties have you encountered in using climate change projections in water management? *(Multiple answers possible)* *

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Climate projections are too uncertain to be useful for long-term planning.
- The projections overestimate the impacts of climate change and are alarming.
- The models are too complex and inaccessible for practical use.
- The predictions are too generalized and not applicable to local or specific contexts.
- The belief that climate change is natural and predictions are not needed.
- Outrage over the economic costs of using forecasts that outweigh the benefits.
- Skepticism about the reliability of data sources or methodologies used in predictions..
- Інше: _____

23. 3. How do you currently integrate climate data into water management? What tools or methodologies are used? *(Multiple answers possible)* *

Виберіть усе, що підходить.

- Reports and research papers on climate change.
- Consultations with meteorological and climate agencies.
- Participation in seminars to maintain awareness on climate issues.
- Relying on national or regional climate adaptation plans and recommendations.
- Use software tools provided by external consultants or partners.
- Use software tools provided by my institution.
- At this point, I am not integrating climate data into our management practices.
- Інше: _____

Final questions.

24. 1. Recall cases where climate change (in the context of water resources) had an impact on everyday life, or simply made a strong unexpected impression.

For example: when I was a child, there were winters when there was enough snow to build full-length tunnels. In recent years, such winters have not been observed in that area.

25. 2. The survey is anonymous and after analyzing the results we will make every effort to better and more clearly communicate scientific climate data to all interested people.
As you know, our team is from Ukraine, and we may not understand, or misunderstand, some aspects of your work. Therefore, we would be grateful if you could leave your contacts.

 Thank you for your contribution and the time you spent on the survey. We believe that our work will be useful for further practical solutions and projects.

Google Форми